

FIRST HELP

Pioneering
technologies
for first responders.

When disasters such as terrorist attacks, earthquakes or tornados happen, first responders (FRs) react to the emergency or crisis call.

Being on the front line in dealing with these situations, rescuers face major dangers daily.

FirstHelp is a Cluster of 3 EU-funded projects developing novel solutions that support first responders in facing multiple dangers.

Among other, these pioneering technologies enhance their sensory skills to better face emergency situations:

- System for electro tactile communication

- Algorithms for assessment of physiological strain based on sensory data
- Mixed reality training system and training guidelines to train medical first responders for mass casualty incidents

- Technologies for real-time positioning

- Smart wearables
- Denoising and image restoration technology
- A portable sensors platform for human-augmented olfaction allowing FRs to identify dangerous gas substances

Join us on the front line to make a difference during emergencies.

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sixthsenseproject.eu

rescuerproject.eu

med1stmr.eu

horizonresultsbooster.eu

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